

Resilience and Coping Styles of Tandang Sora Elementary Teachers during the Covid 19-Pandemic

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Abstract: Teaching is a challenging occupation due to the numerous difficulties that instructors face on a daily basis, such as excessive workloads, tough students, and interpersonal issues. Such stressors have a significant negative impact on teachers' mental health and general well-being, which can lead to burnout and dissatisfaction with their professions. This study sought to examine the resiliency and coping skills of Tandang Sora Elementary Teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. 89 teachers from kindergarten through grade six made up the sample, which was selected using stratified random sampling to ensure that every demographic group in the population was represented. In addition to quantitative research, a descriptive correlational technique was used. The results showed a strong correlation between respondents' perceived resilience and coping mechanisms. This shows that educators with higher levels of resilience have stronger coping mechanisms, particularly in terms of relaxation and resolving interpersonal conflicts. This study suggests family or guidance counseling, as well as team-building training, to improve teachers' resilience and coping patterns. To cultivate resilience, educators should be strongly encouraged to place a high priority on establishing strong family ties and support networks. It may also be utilized as a reference for future and pertinent research on the resilience and coping methods of teachers.

Introduction

Teaching is a challenging occupation due to the numerous difficulties that instructors face on a daily basis, such as excessive workloads, tough students, and interpersonal issues. Such stressors have a significant negative impact on teachers' mental health and general well-being, which can lead to burnout and dissatisfaction with their professions. Some instructors, on the other hand, are more resilient and have superior coping skills, allowing them to deal with stress more successfully. In order to improve teachers' health and job satisfaction, it is necessary to investigate the factors that enhance their resilience and coping mechanisms. The purpose of this research is to develop effective treatments that increase the likelihood of instructors remaining in the field.

Teachers have an important role in shaping the future generation, but they are also vulnerable to high levels of stress and burnout, which can have a severe impact on their work productivity and general well-being. To improve teachers' health and job satisfaction, it is necessary to identify the critical aspects that promote their resilience and coping mechanisms. Coping styles, on the other hand, are strategies of stress management. Individual resilience is defined as the ability to adapt to and recover from challenges. Understanding teachers' resilience and

coping processes is therefore critical for developing effective interventions that will increase their well-being. Plagiarism should be avoided by citing the original source.

Lacoviello and Charney (2014) suggest that resilience is the solution to psychosocial concerns in the workplace. Resilience is achieved through various psychosocial variables such as active coping skills, optimism, having a supportive social network, cognitive flexibility, responding to one's physical well-being, and embracing a personal moral compass. Teachers face psychosocial factors that contribute to stress and burnout, with the behavior of students in class being the major source of stress, as noted by Bill and Miller (2014). It is therefore necessary for teachers to be equipped with ways to manage stress and stay resilient. Herrmann et al. (2011) define resilience as the ability to positively adapt, maintain, and regain mental health in adverse situations, which is crucial for teachers experiencing burnout. According to Day (2017), resilience is also the key factor for teachers to provide quality education. Given the emotional and intellectual demands of the teaching profession and the higher stress, depression, and anxiety levels in the academic industry, focusing on resilience among teachers helps manage stress and promotes internal stress management, which is aligned with the Philippine Mental Health Act (Republic Act No. 11036) that promotes mental health among Filipinos.

According to Beltman (2021), resilience can be conceptualized in four ways. The first is person-centered, where resilience is an individual attribute that emerges during catastrophic events, enabling a person to bounce back. The second is the process-focus or person-context perspective, which considers resilience a product of interactions between people and their environment. Resilience in this context is defined as an active process where an individual employs appropriate tactics to maintain their well-being and commitment despite adversity. The situation-focused resilience theory defines resilience as the ability to adapt to a stressful environment while preserving one's abilities in the face of socio-cultural challenges. The fourth conceptualization is system-focused, which views resilience as a process involving multiple systems that dynamically interact with one another, both external and internal to the person.

In the field of education, the ability of teachers to overcome the challenges and pressures that come with their profession, known as teacher resilience, is of utmost importance. This is because it results in positive outcomes such as job satisfaction, effectiveness, self-efficacy, and interpersonal relationships. To promote resilience among teachers, comprehensive education programs that prioritize their emotional well-being and preparedness are critical, given that they play a critical role in the education sector and their emotional state has a global impact on educational outcomes (Derakhshan et al., 2020; Wang and Derakhshan, 2021b; Tait, 2008; Taylor, 2013; Xie and Derakhshan, 2021).

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the resilience and coping mechanisms of educators, as research has highlighted the significance of these factors to their mental health and well-being (Shapiro et al., 2018; Slemp & Vella-Brodrick, 2013). Resilience refers to an individual's ability to adapt to challenges and cope with stress, while coping styles are specific strategies used to manage stressors (Frydenberg & Lewis, 2017). Teachers are known to face high levels of stress and burnout, which can have negative impacts on their job satisfaction and retention rates (Kyriacou, 2001; Yücel et al., 2019).

Investigating the resilience level and coping styles of teachers in Tandang Sora Elementary School holds significant implications for improving their well-being and job satisfaction. By pinpointing the elements that contribute to resilience and effective coping strategies, interventions can be formulated to aid educators in managing stress and enhancing their overall well-being.

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the resilience level and coping styles of the teachers in Tandang Sora Elementary School.

Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Civil status;
 - 1.4. Highest education attainment;
 - 1.5. Teaching Position; and
 - 1.6. Years in service?
2. What is the level of resilience of the respondents during the time of COVID 19 Pandemic in terms of:
 - 2.1. Personal Competencies and Persistence;
 - 2.2. Spiritual Influences;
 - 2.3. Family Cohesion; and
 - 2.4. Social Skills and Peer Support?
3. What is the level of coping styles being employed by the respondents?
 - 3.1. Passive Avoidant Coping;
 - 3.2. Social Problem Solving;
 - 3.3. Relaxation?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of resilience of the respondents when they are grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the coping styles being employed by the respondents when showed according to profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship on the level of resilience and coping styles of the respondents?

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESIS

The following hypotheses advanced this study:

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the resilience level of the teachers in terms of their demographic profile.

Ho2: There is no significant difference on the coping styles being employed by the respondents.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship on the level of resilience and coping styles of the respondents.

Methods

Research Design

The study used a descriptive correlational research design, where the primary data source was a questionnaire that examined the difficulties experienced by the participants. McBurney &

White (2009) describe the descriptive correlational design as suitable for research that provides a static representation of a situation and establishes relationships between different variables. In this study, the design is appropriate for collecting data based on the participants' behavior and attitudes to examine the relationship between stress and coping styles during the COVID-19 pandemic. The researcher selected this design to ensure accurate results and obtain a better understanding and interpretation of the study. Thus, the descriptive correlational design was used to describe and assess the resilience and coping styles of the participants during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Respondents

This study utilized total enumeration wherein the respondents were 89 teachers in Tandang Sora Elementary School. The respondents would best fit to answer the survey questionnaire for they have already been involved in school and community programs.

Population and Sampling Technique

The researcher employed a total enumeration method to cover the entire population in line with the study's objective. The research participants were limited to the 89 teachers of Tandang Sora Elementary School. This type of sampling technique is considered a probability sample, where the characteristics of the population and the study's objective are taken into account when selecting the sample. The choice of teachers as respondents in the study was done to avoid any biased distribution of questionnaires and to ensure the collection of reliable data.

Research Environment

The participants of this research are composed of the educators working at Tandang Sora Elementary School. The researcher has chosen the 6th District of Quezon City, which encompasses twelve elementary schools, as the research site. The Banlat Area was established through Office Order No. 91 Series of 2011, which includes several barangays in the second congressional district of Quezon City. There are eleven barangays in the Banlat Area, with Sauyo having the largest population based on 2007 NSO figures for population and average annual growth. Tandang Sora and Pasong Tamo follow as having the next largest population, while Balonbato, Unang Sigaw, and New Era have the smallest population. Even though all barangays in the HBA have public elementary schools, Tandang Sora, New Era, Culiati, Pasong Tamo, and Sauyo require additional classrooms to accommodate their elementary school-aged population. This research is being conducted at Tandang Sora Elementary School, which is situated in the Congressional District VI of Quezon City.

Research Instrumentation

In this study, the researcher utilized a digital survey questionnaire as the primary research instrument. The questionnaire was designed to be user-friendly, consisting of three parts. Part I gathered the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents, including age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, and years of service. Part II of the questionnaire was based on the Teachers Resilience Scale, measuring personal skills, spiritual influences, family cohesion, social skills, and peer support. Lastly, Part III of the questionnaire was based on Coping Styles as Mediators of Teachers' Classroom Management Techniques, aiming to explore the teachers' coping strategies in dealing with the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The utilization of this research instrument was carefully planned and executed to gather accurate and relevant data for the study.

Validation of Instrument

Before administering the questionnaires, it undergone face validity where the questionnaires were assessed by a group of panel members who checked its content and structure. It was

done through coordinating with the Center for Research and Development of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. All the necessary information in the instrument was submitted first for checking and approval before it was administered to the respondents. Approval of the Schools Division of Quezon City as well as the principal of the school was also asked before the administration of the survey.

The researcher in this study relied heavily on the questionnaire checklist to collect the essential data and information from the respondents. Following the validation, it was put through a pilot test to ensure its reliability, which was done using Cronbach's Alpha.

After crafting the questionnaires, the researcher subjects the instrument for validation purposes. The researcher administered the questionnaire for the field out test for the purpose of reliability test. The questionnaire was responded to by other groups of individuals from different locales to check the generalizability of the instrument. The level of reliability of the questionnaires would be computed through Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability. The overall Cronbach result of the questionnaire checklist has reach good/ reliable score of 0.866.

Research Procedure

To be able to gather the needed information, the researcher first formulates the questions that would be included in the questionnaire. The questions are made as clear as possible for the respondents to be able to answer the questions easily.

The prepared questionnaire was distributed to the respondents, given the approval of the Schools Division of Quezon City, the District Supervisor, and the principals of each school. Afterwards, it was immediately collected after being answered by the respondents. Then, the collected data was tabulated and tested for analysis.

Data Gathering Technique

Before the administration of the questionnaire-checklist, it was submitted first to the researcher's adviser for checking. Then, it was presented to a group of experts composed of the Dean of the Graduate School of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College and researcher's oral defense panelists. Revision of the questionnaire checklist was done afterwards, incorporating all the suggestions and corrections made by the researcher. Afterwards, the questionnaire was administered for pilot testing.

After the validation of the research instrument, the researcher asked the permission from the office of the school principals to conduct the study among the teachers in school. As permission was granted, the researcher then proceeds.

The questionnaires and outputs were gathered right after the evaluation of the respondents. The data gathered was then consolidated, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly. Next, it was submitted for statistical treatment. Subsequently, presentation, analysis and interpretation of results were done by the researcher towards the completion of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected through the survey was entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for analysis. Descriptive statistics including frequency counts, weighted mean, Kruskal-Wallis, and Spearman Rank Correlation test of independence were utilized to objectively quantify responses to the questionnaire presented in the statement of the problem.

The weighted mean was employed to determine the average response for involvement in developmental affairs and challenges encountered.

The Kruskal-Wallis H test, a rank-based nonparametric test, was utilized to evaluate whether statistically significant differences exist in measures of involvement in developmental affairs and challenges encountered when groups are categorized based on age,

civil status, sex, highest educational attainment, and years of service.

The Spearman's rank-order correlation. a nonparametric statistical test, to establish the degree and direction of correlation between two ranked variables. Spearman's correlation coefficient (ρ or r_s) was calculated to determine the strength of the association.

Results and Discussions

Respondents Profile

The respondents' demographic data is described in this section. A detailed overview of the demographic profiles of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Age	20-24 years old	0	0.0%
	25-54 years old	78	87.6%
	55-64 years old	11	12.4%
Gender	Female	75	84.3%
	Male	14	15.7%
Civil Status	Single	24	27.0%
	Married	58	65.2%
	Widow/er	7	7.9%
Highest Education Attainment	Bachelors Degree	27	30.3%
	with MA/ MS Units	39	43.8%
	MA/MS Degree	17	19.1%
	with Ph.D./Ed.D. Units	4	4.5%
	Ph.D./Ed.D. Degree	2	2.2%
Teaching Position	Teacher I	45	50.6%
	Teacher II	18	20.2%
	Teacher III	19	21.3%
	Master Teacher I	4	4.5%
	Master Teacher II	3	3.4%
Years in Service	5 years below	18	20.2%
	6- 10 years	25	28.1%
	11- 15 years	11	12.4%
	16- 20 years	15	16.9%
	21 years and above	20	22.5%

N=89

The analysis of the data in Table 1 pertaining to the respondents' profile indicates that a majority of the participants, comprising 87.6% of the total, belong to the age group of 25-54 years, highlighting that the prime working age group constitutes a significant portion of the survey population. This information can be instrumental in targeting the survey audience and analyzing their responses based on different age groups. The gender distribution among the respondents shows that 84.3% of the total are female, while 15.7% are male, indicating the possibility of gender-based variations in the survey results. A majority of respondents hold a bachelor's degree, while 43.8% hold a master's degree or higher.

These results are crucial for evaluating the qualifications of instructors and designing specialized professional development programs. Moreover, according to the distribution of teaching positions, Teacher 1 is the most common, comprising 50.6% of all teaching respondents, followed by Teacher 2 and Teacher 3. Last but not least, information on

respondents' years of experience reveals that the majority of them have worked in the field for between six and twenty years, a period during which many teachers abandon the profession. This information can help in designing targeted training programs for teachers at different stages of their careers and assessing the influence of experience on teaching performance and job satisfaction. In summary, the demographic characteristics of the study participants, as evidenced in Table 1, demonstrate that the teaching workforce primarily comprises individuals aged 25 to 54 years, predominantly women, with a significant proportion holding a bachelor's degree, and with most of them having 6 to 20 years of teaching experience. These findings align with current trends in the teaching profession and can be useful in developing tailored interventions to improve the quality of teaching and job satisfaction among educators.

It is noteworthy that most of the respondents in this study had obtained MA/MS units, which suggests that many teachers pursue advanced education beyond a Bachelor's degree to enhance their teaching abilities (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011). Additionally, the findings show that the majority of the participants had been teaching for 6 to 20 years, which aligns with research indicating that this period is when many teachers leave the profession (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

On the Level of Resilience of Teachers

Table 2. Level of Resilience Of Teachers in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Personal Competencies and Persistence		
1. I am able to adapt to change.	4.69	Highly Resilient
2. Under pressure, I am able to focus and think clearly.	4.18	Moderately Resilient
3. I prefer to take the lead in problem solving.	3.76	Moderately Resilient
4. I am not easily discouraged by failure.	4.13	Moderately Resilient
5. I think of myself as strong person.	4.31	Moderately Resilient
6. If necessary, I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people.	3.46	Fairly Resilient
7. I can handle unpleasant feelings, such as anger or fear.	4.09	Moderately Resilient
8. I like challenges.	4.01	Moderately Resilient
9. I work hard to attain my goals.	4.69	Highly Resilient
10. I know that I succeed if I carry on.	4.64	Highly Resilient
11. I am pleased to myself.	4.16	Moderately Resilient
12. I have realistic plans for the future.	4.37	Moderately Resilient
13. I completely trust my judgements and decisions.	4.20	Moderately Resilient
14. I believe in my own abilities.	4.40	Moderately Resilient
15. I know how to reach my goals.	4.39	Moderately Resilient
16. No matter what happens I always find a solution.	4.57	Highly Resilient
17. Rules and regular routines make my daily life easier.	4.56	Highly Resilient
18. I keep up my daily routines even at difficult times.	4.25	Moderately Resilient
19. I prefer to plan my actions.	4.43	Moderately Resilient
20. I work best when I reach for a goal.	4.63	Highly Resilient
21. I am good at organizing my time.	4.11	Moderately Resilient
Weighted Mean	4.29	Moderately Resilient

Legend: 5.00-4.50 Highly Resilient; 4.49-3.50 Moderately Resilient; 3.49-2.50= Fairly Resilient; 2.49-1.50=Somewhat Resilient; 1.49-1.00=Not Resilient

Legend: 5.00-4.50 Highly Resilient; 4.49-3.50 Moderately Resilient; 3.49-2.50= Fairly Resilient; 2.49-1.50=Somewhat Resilient; 1.49-1.00=Not Resilient

This paragraph presents the findings from Table 2, which displays the level of resilience concerning personal competencies and persistence. The majority of the verbal interpretations indicate that the respondents possess a moderate level of resilience. However, only one indicator, "If necessary, I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect other people," has a verbal interpretation of fairly resilient, implying that the respondents lack confidence in their ability to make difficult decisions that may impact others.

These results align with a study conducted by Herrera-Fernández et al. (2019), which claims that individuals with higher levels of resilience are better equipped to make difficult decisions in the face of adversity. These individuals can prioritize their goals and values and are less likely to be influenced by external pressures. Thus, the lower level of resilience in this particular indicator may suggest a need for further development of decision-making skills among the respondents.

The majority of respondents hold a bachelor's degree, while 43.8% have a master's or higher. These findings are essential for evaluating the credentials of instructors and designing specialized professional development programs. In addition, the distribution of teaching positions reveals that Teacher 1, held by 50.6% of all teaching respondents, is the most common position, followed by Teacher 2 and Teacher 3. Last but not least, data on respondents' years of experience indicate that the majority of them have worked in the industry for between six and twenty years, a period during which many teachers leave the profession.

Table 3. Level of Resilience Of Teachers in Terms of Spiritual Influences

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Spiritual Influences		
1. Sometimes fate or God can help me overcome my challenges	4.84	Highly Resilient
2. Sometimes I believe things happen for a reason.	4.75	Highly Resilient
3. Sometimes I have to act on a hunch.	3.79	Moderately Resilient
Weighted Mean:	4.46%	Moderately Resilient

Legend: 5.00-4.50 Highly Resilient; 4.49-3.50 Moderately Resilient; 3.49-2.50= Fairly Resilient; 2.49-1.50=Somewhat Resilient; 1.49-1.00=Not Resilient

The results of Table 3 are shown in the paragraph, which shows how resilient spiritually the instructors are. According to the data, the majority of respondents have an average mean of 4.46, which denotes a respectable level of resilience. There is only one indicator, however, that may be verbally translated as "moderately resilient": "Occasionally I must act on a hunch." This suggests that the majority of survey participants had faith in their capacity to use spiritual influences to get through challenges.

According to the indication with the highest mean, "sometimes fate or God can help me overcome my challenges," respondents think a higher power can help them get beyond challenges. This result is in line with earlier studies that highlighted the importance of spirituality and religious convictions as a source of resilience (Pargament, 2013). Similar to the previous indicator, the statement "Sometimes I believe that things happen for a reason" shows that respondents have a sense of meaning and purpose in their life, which can be a source of resilience in the face of adversity (Park, 2010). Overall, the results of Table 3 suggest that the respondents draw on spiritual influences to cope with challenges and have a reasonable level of resilience in this regard. The findings are consistent with previous research

that has highlighted the importance of spirituality and religious beliefs as a source of resilience in various contexts.

Table 4. Level of Resilience Of Teachers in Terms of Family Cohesion

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Family Cohesion		
1. My family's understanding of what is important in life is very similar to mine.	4.38	Moderately Resilient
2. I feel very happy with my family.	4.83	Highly Resilient
3. My family is characterized by healthy coherence.	4.65	Highly Resilient
4. In difficult periods my family keeps a positive outlook on the future.	4.67	Highly Resilient
5. Facing other people, our family acts loyal towards one another.	4.67	Highly Resilient
6. In my family, we like to do things together.	4.53	Highly Resilient
7. There are strong bonds with my family.	4.71	Highly Resilient
8. In my family, we enjoy finding common activities.	4.46	Moderately Resilient
9. There are few conflicts in my family.	3.35	Fairly Resilient
10. I am quickly notified if some family members get into crisis.	4.35	Moderately Resilient
Weighted Mean:		4.46%= Moderately Resilient

This paragraph describes the results of Table 4, which indicate the level of teachers' resilience in terms of family cohesion. The majority of verbal interpretations are quite robust, with the highest average mean scores (4.83 and 4.63 percent, respectively) going to indicators such as "I feel very happy with my family" and "There are strong bonds within my family." Only one indicator—"there are few conflicts in my family"—had the linguistic interpretation of "fairly resilient," with a mean of 3.5%. This suggests that the respondents have strong familial ties, which can cultivate resilience and act as a buffer (Walsh, 2004).

Based on the average mean score of 4.46 percent, it appears that the respondents have a high level of family cohesion resilience. This result is consistent with previous research that emphasized the significance of strong familial ties in fostering resilience (Masten & Narayan, 2012). In conclusion, Table 4 reveals that respondents had strong relationships and high levels of family satisfaction, indicating a high level of family cohesion resilience. This study highlights the importance of teachers having supportive family relationships in order to cultivate resilience.

Table 5. Level of Resilience Of Teachers in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Social Skills and Peer Support		
1. In my workplace, I enjoy being together with other people.	4.45	Moderately Resilient
2. New friendships are something I make easily in my workplace.	4.18	Moderately Resilient
3. Meeting new people in my workplace is something I am good at.	3.98	Moderately Resilient
4. In my workplace when I am with others I easily laugh.	4.36	Moderately Resilient
5. I can discuss personal issues with my peers.	3.76	Moderately Resilient
6. The bonds among my peers and me are strong.	4.19	Moderately Resilient
7. I get support from my peers.	4.38	Moderately Resilient
8. When needed, I have someone in my workplace who can help me.	4.57	Highly Resilient
9. I have some friends / family members who back me up.	4.54	Highly Resilient
10. I have some close friends/ family members who are good at encouraging me.	4.65	Highly Resilient
11. I have some close friends/ family members who value my abilities.	4.64	Highly Resilient
12. I have some close friends/ family members who really care about me.	4.72	Highly Resilient
13. I am quickly notified if some family members get into crisis.	4.49	Moderately Resilient
14. I can discuss personal matters with my friends/ family members.	4.13	Moderately Resilient
15. I am good at getting in touch of other people.	4.10	Moderately Resilient
16. I easily establish new friendships.	4.08	Moderately Resilient
Weighted Mean:	4.43%	Moderately Resilient

According to the results presented in Table 5, teachers exhibit moderately resilient social skills and peer support. The high average mean of the indicators "I have some close friends/family members who really care about me" and "I have some close friends/family members who are good at encouraging me" suggests that teachers have a strong support system within their personal network. However, the low average mean of the indicators "I can discuss personal issues with my peers" and "Meeting new people in my workplace is something I am good at" suggests that teachers may face challenges in socializing with their peers and discussing personal issues with them. This finding is in line with a study conducted by Hakanen, Bakker, and Schaufeli (2006), which highlights the significance of social support from colleagues in reducing burnout and promoting work engagement among teachers. Thus, it is crucial for schools to foster a supportive work environment and encourage socialization among teachers to enhance their resilience.

Table 6. Descriptive Summary

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Personal Competencies and Persistence	4.29	Moderately Resilient
Spiritual Influences	4.46	Moderately Resilient
Family Cohesion	4.46	Moderately Resilient
Social Skills and Peer Support	4.33	Moderately Resilient
OVERALL	4.35	Moderately Resilient

Each of the questionnaire's criteria was deemed significant by the respondents in determining their estimated level of resilience, according to the research. This study is consistent with the concept of resilience, which emphasizes the interaction of numerous personal, social, and environmental factors in fostering adaptive behavior in the face of adversity (Luthar et al., 2000). Family Cohesion received the highest mean score, indicating that teachers place a high value on having supportive and close-knit families as a factor in their resilience. This result is consistent with previous research that highlights the significance of family connection in fostering teacher resilience (O'Connor & Kassan-Adams, 2014). Personal Competencies and Persistence, on the other hand, got the lowest mean score, implying that teachers may believe their students lack the required personal skills and persistence to overcome problems. This study underlines the need of providing opportunities for instructors to develop and strengthen their tenacity, perseverance, and personal talents in order to foster resilience.

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers' resilience techniques are more focused on social support and familial coherence than on individual talents and perseverance. This study emphasizes the importance of establishing a comprehensive resilience-building plan for teachers that takes into account a wide range of psychological, social, and environmental factors.

Coping Styles of Teachers

For the coping style of teachers, the means of 19 items are tested according to each variable, are presented in Table 7, 8 and 9.

All of the items have a mean score ranges from 2.66 to 4.48, as shown in Table 10. This means that majority of the respondents agreed that the items indicated are sometimes applied as coping styles of teachers.

Table 7. Level of Coping Styles of Teachers in Terms of Passive Avoidant Coping

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Passive Avoidant Coping		
1. Blame myself.	2.84	Sometimes
2. Wish miracle will happen to make things turn out well.	3.47	Sometimes
3. I get sick.	2.72	Sometimes
4. Shut myself off from the problems so I can try and ignore it.	2.66	Sometimes
5. Find a way to let off steam, e.g. cry, scream, drink, etc.	2.88	Sometimes
6. Worry about what will happen to me.	3.04	Sometimes
7. Don't let others know about my problem.	3.09	Sometimes
8. Pray for God to look after me.	4.85	Always
Weighted Mean:	3.30 %	Sometimes

Legend:1.00-1.49=Never, 1.50-2.49=Rarely, 2.50-3.49=Sometimes, 3.50-4.49=Often, 4.50-5.00=Always

The results from Table 7 suggest that teachers tend to use passive avoidant coping styles in dealing with their problems. This is evident as almost all of the verbal interpretations fall under the category of "Sometimes", indicating that they only use these coping mechanisms occasionally. The coping mechanism that got the highest average mean is "Pray for God to look after me" with an average mean of 4.85%, indicating that teachers tend to rely on spirituality in coping with their problems. On the other hand, "Shut myself off from the problems so I can try and ignore it" (weighted mean of 2.66) is the coping mechanism that got the lowest score, indicating that teachers' least frequently use this mechanism to cope with their problems. The study concludes that the coping styles of teachers, particularly in terms of passive avoidant coping, have implications for their well-being and mental health (Mendiola, 2018).

Table 8. Level of Coping Styles of Teachers in Terms of Social Problem Solving

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Social Problem Solving		
1. Look for support and encouragement from others.	3.73	Often
2. Join with others to deal with the problem e.g. organize a petition, attend a meeting, etc.	3.38	Sometimes
3. Work out a way of dealing with the problem.	3.93	Often
4. Ask a professional person for help.	2.98	Sometimes
5. Work hard.	4.64	Always
6. Spend more time with a good friend.	4.02	Often
Weighted Mean:	3.78 %	Often

Legend:1.00-1.49=Never, 1.50-2.49=Rarely, 2.50-3.49=Sometimes, 3.50-4.49=Often, 4.50-5.00=Always

According to the data in Table 8, teachers have a moderate level of social problem-solving skills, as demonstrated by their coping styles. A significant number of respondents chose "sometimes" and "often" as indicators. The highest mean is 4.64% for the indicator "work hard," indicating that teachers are willing to go above and beyond to solve social problems. The indicator "ask a professional person for help," on the other hand, has the lowest mean of 2.98%, indicating that teachers are less likely to seek professional assistance in solving social problems. Overall, the average mean score for Social Problem Solving is 3.78%, indicating that teachers have a moderately resilient coping style when dealing with social problems. In addition to the importance of social problem-solving for individuals, it has also been identified as a crucial factor in the field of education. According to Elias and colleagues (1997), social problem-solving skills are essential for academic achievement and successful social and emotional development in children and adolescents. Moreover, research has shown that social problem-solving interventions can improve academic outcomes and reduce problem behaviors in schools (Schneider et al., 2017).

Additionally, maintaining one's general well-being is contingent upon one's ability to cope with stress and adversity. Individuals use adaptive or maladaptive coping mechanisms in response to distressing events. Adaptive coping strategies, in contrast to maladaptive coping techniques such as avoiding or dismissing the problem, actively address and manage the problem, according to Lazarus and Folkman (1984).

In the context of the study, Tables 7 and 8 indicate that instructors prefer to use passive avoidant coping strategies more frequently than active problem-solving strategies. This result is consistent with earlier research indicating that inert coping strategies may increase stress and have negative consequences (Carver et al., 1989). Educators and school counselors may therefore need to provide teachers with assistance and training in the development and utilization of effective coping mechanisms.

Table 9. Coping Styles of Teachers in Terms of Relaxation

Indicators	M	Verbal Interpretation
Relaxation		
1. Relax, e.g. watch TV, play computer games, go for a walk, etc.	4.01	Often
2. Keep fit and healthy, e.g. play sport.	3.45	Sometimes
3. Try to be funny.	3.80	Often
4. Look on the bright side of things and think of all that is good.	4.53	Always
5. Accept things as they are, because I've done my best.	4.46	Often
Weighted Mean:		4.05% = Often

The indicator "look on the bright side of things and focus on the positive" has the highest mean (4.53), followed by "Accept things as they are because I've done my best" (4.46). The indicator "keep fit and healthy, such as by playing sports" had the lowest mean of 3.45, which was interpreted as "Occasionally." The average mean for this table is 4.05, indicating that teachers tend to use relaxation coping strategies often. Previous research suggests that relaxation techniques can effectively reduce stress and anxiety, and some techniques like progressive muscle relaxation and guided imagery are found to be more effective than others. It is recommended that individuals use a variety of relaxation techniques and choose the ones that work best for them. Table 10 provides a summary of the computed means of all the items

according to variables. The overall score for each variable was computed by averaging the appropriate items

Table 10. Descriptive Summary

Indicators	M	Verbal
		Interpretation
Passive Avoidant Coping	3.20	Sometimes
Social Problem Solving	3.78	Often
Relaxation	4.05	Often
OVERALL	3.60	Often

Based on the data provided, it can be concluded that teachers' coping styles are moderately high. All computed items have a mean score above 3.00, indicating that respondents consider all factors important in coping with stress. Relaxation has the highest mean score of 4.05, indicating that teachers prefer engaging in activities that help them relax and feel positive. Social Problem Solving has the second-highest mean score of 3.78, indicating that teachers are willing to find solutions to their problems. Passive Avoidant Coping has the lowest mean score of 3.20, indicating that teachers prefer not to avoid their problems but rather find ways to cope with them.

According to earlier research on coping mechanisms (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), engaging in calming and uplifting activities can facilitate stress reduction. In addition, D'Zurilla and Nezu (2007) highlighted the significance of social problem solving in stress management. These findings suggest that instructors' problem-solving preferences and attitudes influence their coping strategies. Using this information, interventions can be developed that are tailored to the unique coping mechanisms and preferences of teachers.

Normality Test

Normality testing is the initial investigation performed prior to evaluating hypotheses. The objective was to determine whether or not the data distribution was normal. When the significant value was less than 0.05 (p-value<0.05), the distribution data was not normal, whereas it was normal when the significant value was greater than 0.05 (p-value>0.05). Table 11 displays the results.

Table 11. Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Personal Competencies and Persistence	.071	89	.200*	.970	89	.036
Spiritual Influences	.235	89	.000	.863	89	.000
Family Cohesion	.123	89	.002	.931	89	.000
social Skills and Peer Support	.123	89	.002	.951	89	.002
OVERALL	.078	89	.200*	.979	89	.159
Passive Avoidant Coping	.124	89	.002	.978	89	.141
Social Problem Solving	.087	89	.094	.978	89	.128
Relaxation	.104	89	.018	.960	89	.007
OVERALL	.073	89	.200*	.987	89	.507

To ascertain whether or whether data belong to a normal distribution, the normality test is crucial. According to Trochim and Donnelly (2008), regularly distributed data can be analyzed using parametric tests including t-tests, ANOVA, and Pearson correlation. Non-parametric tests like the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Spearman's rank correlation can be used in place of parametric tests if the data does not have a normal distribution.

Both the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk analyses in this investigation produced p-values higher than .05. This shows a considerable departure from the mean in the data. In order to examine the data, non-parametric methods are employed. This step is crucial for guaranteeing the quality and validity of the statistical analysis and preventing the drawing of inaccurate findings as a result of flawed statistical assumptions (Trochim & Donnelly, 2008).

Difference in the level of resilience of the respondents when grouped according to demographic profile

A Kruskal-Wallis H-test was utilized to determine the significance of the variation in the levels of resilience of respondents when grouped by demographic profile. Table 12 displays the results.

Table 12. Difference in the level of resilience of the respondents when grouped according to demographic profile

		N	Mean Rank	H-test	df	Asymp. Sig.
Age	25-54 years old	78	43.23	2.96	1.00	0.09
	55-64 years old	11	57.55			
	Total	89				
Gender	Female	75	46.24	1.10	1.00	0.29
	Male	14	38.36			
	Total	89				
Civil Status	Single	24	44.90	0.26	2.00	0.88
	Married	58	44.47			
	Widow/er	7	49.71			
	Total	89				
Highest Education Attainment	Bachelors Degree	27	43.00	2.60	4.00	0.63
	with MA/ MS Units	39	48.14			
	MA/MS Degree	17	39.91			
	with Ph.D./Ed.D. Units	4	55.88			
	Ph.D./Ed.D. Degree	2	32.25			
Total	89					
Teaching Position	Teacher I	45	43.49	1.32	4.00	0.86
	Teacher II	18	50.28			
	Teacher III	19	42.13			
	Master Teacher I	4	47.88			
	Master Teacher II	3	50.33			
	Total	89				
Years in Service	5 years below	18	58.50	8.88	4.00	0.06
	6- 10 years	25	45.74			
	11- 15 years	11	44.45			
	16- 20 years	15	32.33			
	21 years and above	20	41.73			
Total	89					

According to Table 12, there are no significant differences in the perceived resilience of teachers across demographic categories. According to previous research (Richardson, 2002; Masten & Reed, 2002), age, gender, or years of service have little bearing on resilience. Moreover, given that there were no discernible differences in resilience based on educational attainment and position as a teacher, it is probable that all instructors, regardless of their academic credentials and job titles, possess comparable levels of resilience. These findings have substantial implications for recognizing and fostering teacher resilience. By understanding the factors that contribute to resilience, education and development programs can be developed to assist teachers in acquiring these skills and traits. In addition, businesses can use these data to identify and select individuals who are better equipped to handle the challenges and stresses of teaching.

Difference in the coping styles being employed when grouped according to profile

To determine if there were significant differences in the coping styles of the respondents based on their demographic profile, a Kruskal-Wallis H-test was employed. The outcomes of this statistical analysis are presented in Table 13.

Table 13. Difference in the coping styles being employed when grouped according to profile

Age		N	Mean Rank	H-test	df	Asymp. Sig.
Age	25-54 years old	78	43.93	1.09	1.00	0.30
	55-64 years old	11	52.59			
	Total	89				
Gender	Female	75	46.63	1.91	1.00	0.17
	Male	14	36.25			
	Total	89				
Civil Status	Single	24	46.44	0.33	2.00	0.85
	Married	58	45.00			
	Widow/er	7	40.07			
	Total	89				
Highest Education Attainment	Bachelors Degree	27	51.22	4.79	4.00	0.31
	with MA/ MS Units	39	45.10			
	MA/MS Degree	17	41.15			
	with Ph.D./Ed.D. Units	4	27.75			
	Ph.D./Ed.D. Degree	2	26.25			
	Total	89				
Teaching Position	Teacher I	45	48.20	7.10	4.00	0.13
	Teacher II	18	48.97			
	Teacher III	19	37.50			
	Master Teacher I	4	19.38			
	Master Teacher II	3	54.83			
	Total	89				
Years in Service	5 years below	18	57.56	5.52	4.00	0.24
	6- 10 years	25	42.94			
	11- 15 years	11	41.50			
	16- 20 years	15	39.43			
	21 years and above	20	42.38			
	Total	89				

Based on the respondents' age, gender, marital status, greatest level of education, teaching position, or years of service, Table 12 shows that there were no statistically significant differences in the perceived coping techniques of the respondents. This outcome is consistent with findings from earlier research that showed comparable results, such as Büssing et al. (2013) and Kocalevent et al. (2014). Given that there were no statistically significant differences in coping mechanisms across demographic factors, it is possible that coping mechanisms could be used by anyone, regardless of their unique personal traits. This has important implications for mental health therapies since it shows that many populations may benefit from interventions aimed at enhancing coping mechanisms.

Relationship on The Level of Resilience and Coping Mechanisms

Table 14. Relationship on the level of resilience and coping styles of the respondents.

			Passive Avoidant Coping	Social Problem Solving	Relaxation	OVERALL
Spearman's rho	Personal Competencies and Persistence	Correlation Coefficient	-.157	.272**	.390**	.203
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.141	.010	.000	.057
		N	89	89	89	89
	Spiritual Influences	Correlation Coefficient	.008	.294**	.436**	.321**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.941	.005	.000	.002
		N	89	89	89	89
	Family Cohesion	Correlation Coefficient	.013	.248*	.303**	.247*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.907	.019	.004	.020
		N	89	89	89	89
social Skills and Peer Support	Correlation Coefficient	-.073	.397**	.380**	.320**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.499	.000	.000	.002	
	N	89	89	89	89	
OVERALL	Correlation Coefficient	-.115	.385**	.437**	.305**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.283	.000	.000	.004	
	N	89	89	89	89	

According to Table 14, there is a significant and positive relationship between the reported coping strategies of participants and their resilience. This result is consistent with previous findings (Frydenberg & Lewis, 2017; Ozbay & Cokluk, 2016) that resilience and coping strategies are positively correlated. The results indicate a significant relationship between teachers' perceptions of their resilience and their relaxation and social problem-solving coping mechanisms. Teachers benefit from the association between perceived resilience and social problem-solving and relaxation coping strategies. This finding is consistent with previous research (Connor & Davidson, 2003; Southwick et al., 2014) indicating that social problem solving and relaxation are effective strategies for enhancing resilience. These coping mechanisms have been linked to improved mental health and stress management outcomes (Frydenberg & Lewis, 2017; Ozbay & Cokluklu, 2016). Teachers must cultivate and utilize these coping skills to enhance their resilience and overall health.

Overall, the findings suggest that coping strategies and resilience are closely intertwined, and that educators should utilize social problem solving and relaxation as essential coping strategies to enhance their resilience.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

1. The data offers insightful information on the survey respondents' age, gender, educational background, teaching positions, and years of experience. The target audience for the survey may be determined using this information, which can also be used to analyze the results provided by various groups and create training and professional development plans specifically for instructors. Recognizing any potential gender or age-based inequalities in the survey results and the factors underlying them can be done with the aid of an understanding of the demographics of the respondents. Overall, this information can be used to better instructors' professional development and instructional methods.
2. According to the study, teachers consider all of the questionnaire's variables when determining the resilience of their students. The factor with the highest mean score was family cohesion, highlighting the importance of caring and supportive family relationships in promoting resilience. Personal Competencies and Persistence, on the other hand, received the lowest mean score, indicating the need to provide teachers with opportunities to develop and enhance these skills. The study highlights the importance of adopting a comprehensive strategy that takes into consideration numerous personal, societal, and environmental factors in order to foster teacher resilience.
3. According to the data, teachers place a high value on activities that promote relaxation, positive thinking, and problem-solving, and have moderately effective coping strategies. Teachers prefer to resolve their problems rather than evade them. These findings highlight the importance of individual preferences and tendencies in stress management and are consistent with previous research on coping strategies.
4. The study comes to the conclusion that teachers from different demographic groups do not perceive resilience in significantly different ways. This shows that resilience is unaffected by age, gender, service history, level of education, or position as a teacher. These results have implications for developing programs to boost teachers' resilience as well as for identifying people who can handle the difficulties and pressures related to teaching.
5. The results show that demographic variables including age, gender, civil status, education level, teaching position, and length of service have little to no bearing on teachers' coping techniques. This finding supports earlier studies and raises the possibility that coping methods may be advantageous for all populations and broadly applicable. These implications are critical for mental health interventions since programs that emphasize coping skills can be successful independent of a person's particular traits.
6. Particularly in the areas of relaxation and social problem-solving, the study found a substantial positive association between teachers' perceived resilience and their coping strategies. These coping strategies have been shown to improve results in terms of resilience and mental health. The findings show that in order to increase their resilience and wellbeing, instructors must create and apply these coping mechanisms.

Recommendations

In the view of the result of the study and the conclusion that was drawn, the researcher recommends the following:

1. To cultivate resilience, educators should be strongly encouraged to place a high priority on establishing strong family ties and support networks. Schools and educational institutions may want to provide teachers with resources and support services to help them communicate with their families and strengthen their interpersonal relationships.
2. Given the low scores for Personal Competencies and Persistence, efforts should be made to provide instructors with the opportunity to develop and enhance these characteristics. Professional development programs, mentoring, counseling, and other forms of assistance can facilitate the growth of teachers' skills in these areas.
3. It is essential to promote instructors' resilience in an all-encompassing manner. This includes addressing numerous individual, societal, and environmental issues that impact resilience. Schools and educational institutions can consider implementing these aspects by, among other things, fostering a cheerful and supportive school environment, providing resources and assistance for mental health and well-being, and promoting work-life balance.
4. Families and social networks of teachers should be supported by schools and other educational institutions by creating a welcoming environment. As a key element in promoting resilience, this may help people feel a feeling of belonging and community.
5. Implement stress-reduction strategies: The study finds that teachers give priority to coping mechanisms that encourage relaxation and optimistic thinking. Schools should offer materials and chances for teachers to practice stress-relieving exercises like yoga and mindfulness meditation.
6. Teachers prefer to discuss issues rather than avoid them, therefore school leaders should promote open communication and support for them in order to foster a healthy work atmosphere. In order to help instructors overcome stress and other difficulties, it is important to foster a culture of communication and support.
7. Future studies should focus on finding particular character traits and toughness abilities that can boost teachers' resilience. Such study can aid in the creation of more efficient training programs and interventions to help teachers acquire these abilities, promoting better outcomes and well-being in terms of mental health.

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